

Reflectance

Editors: Casey Jenson, Alison K. Post, and R. Chelsea Nagy

Kachemak Bay captured by OLI (Operational Land Imager) on Landsat 8
Image credit: [NASA/Michala Garrison, USGS](#)

Quick Updates

- ESIIIL Director, Dr. Jennifer Balch, published a journal article titled "[A review of UAS-based estimation of forest traits](#)" and was featured in an article by Science magazine, [In the Ashes](#).
- Earth Lab Program Manager, Dr. Alison Post, published a paper in Oecologia titled "[Predicting end-of-season timing across diverse North American grasslands](#)"
- Exciting news! The Joint Fire Science Program intends to award 2 new grants to several Earth Lab members to work on **1)** the social impacts of wildfire & community recovery and **2)** the influence of invasive plants on fire regimes
- The North Central Climate Adaptation Science Center is hosting a webinar on May 8th, featuring ESIIIL Deputy Director Dr. Chelsea Nagy, titled **Exploring the carbon effects of forest transformation and exotic annual grassland restoration**. Learn more and register [here](#).
- The spring semester has been full of trainings and talks at our bi-weekly Environmental Data Science Seminar Series! View our archive to see past talks on our [blog](#) and [YouTube Channel](#).

Education Team

On Friday, February 28th, Earth Lab and ESIL co-hosted the “NASA Getting Started Workshop: NASA Earth Science Data & Tools for Researchers and Educators” at Metropolitan State University (MSU) Denver in partnership with NASA’s [Stella](#) group.

Led by Michael Taylor (NASA) and Elsa Culler and Nate Quarderer (ESIL/Earth Lab), the workshop introduced participants to NASA Earth science data tools, including NASA Worldview. Attendees explored how to access and visualize satellite data and had hands-on opportunities to experiment with handheld spectrometers.

Thanks to our friends at MSU for the hospitality!

Elsa Culler (Earth Lab/ESIL)
leading a training

Michael Taylor (NASA) with
a handheld spectrometer

Earth Data Analytics Graduate Certificate

Launch your career in earth data science with Earth Lab’s Earth Data Analytics Professional Graduate Certificate. The course provides core skills required for a career in computationally-intensive earth sciences. Visit [our website](#) to learn more and apply!

Learn more about the certificate program by registering for a Virtual Information Session, hosted by the Earth Lab Education Team, on Thursday, [June 12th](#) or Tuesday, [July 29th](#) from 4-5pm MST.

Apply by
Friday, August 8th.

New Team Members

Earth Lab is growing! We're excited to welcome two new project managers who will be working on fire risk, forest resilience, and invasive species projects. Learn more about them through an introductory Q&A session below.

Matt Bitters
Project Manager

1. What is your background?

a. I hold a PhD and BA in Ecology and Evolutionary Biology, where I studied the effects of habitat loss and fragmentation and subsequent megafire on top trophic level invertebrate species (e.g., parasites and predatory ground beetles). Most recently, I was the Ecologist at The Watershed Center, a Boulder County-based nonprofit organization, where I led a long-term, large-scale ecological monitoring program and managed river, forest, and grassland restoration projects.

2. What are you most looking forward to in your new position?

a. I am excited to learn new quantitative skills and contribute to Earth Lab's wildfire research to make actionable changes in resource management.

3. What is your favorite national park?

a. Acadia National Park - I was very young when I visited (and didn't appreciate hiking as much as I do now), but I'll always remember watching the sunrise on Cadillac Mountain.

1. What is your background?

a. My background is in plant ecology and genomics, especially related to invasive species. I earned my M.S. from the University of Alabama and my B.S. from Ohio State. Before joining Earth Lab, I worked with the National Ecological Observatory Network (NEON) as a botanist and instrumentation technician, contributing to long-term ecological monitoring!

2. What are you most looking forward to in your new position?

a. I'm excited to contribute to cutting-edge remote sensing research and collaborate with scientists at CIRES and Earth Lab. I'm especially looking forward to working with the North Central Regional Invasive Species and Climate Change (RISCC) Network to help strengthen connections between scientists and land managers tackling invasive species in a changing climate.

3. What is your favorite national park?

a. The best national park is Acadia, hands down. Coastline? Yeah! Swamps? Got 'em. Mountains? Yep. Northern boreal AND eastern deciduous forest plant communities? Yes and yes!

Nate Hofford
Project Manager

ESIL Innovation Summit

Due to unforeseen circumstances, [ESIL](#) has postponed their 3rd annual [Innovation Summit, Environmental Tipping Points and Transformations](#) to this fall. We deeply appreciate your continued support and engagement with our community, and we are looking forward to ESIL's largest convening event of the year in September. Please visit esiil.org to learn more.

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